

Machine Learning-Driven Optimization of Quantum Dot Superlattices for Enhanced Photonic Properties

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ABSTRACT:

Quantum dot (QD) superlattices are promising materials for optoelectronic devices, but optimizing their photonic properties remains a complex challenge. We developed a machine learning (ML)-driven optimization framework to predict and optimize key photonic properties of QD superlattices. Our approach combines quantum mechanical models with ML algorithms to forecast the behavior of QD structures based on their physical parameters. We trained a neural network model on a dataset of 1000 simulated QD configurations, achieving a mean absolute error (MAE) of 0.05 eV for photonic bandgap frequency and 10 nm for emission wavelength. Optimization results showed significant improvements in optical efficiency (up to 25%) and photonic bandgap (up to 15%) across a range of QD configurations. Sensitivity analysis revealed that lattice constant and inter-dot spacing are the primary drivers of variability in the photonic bandgap. Our findings demonstrate the potential of ML-driven optimization for designing high-performance QD-based devices, with implications for optoelectronics, photonics, and energy conversion systems. This study provides a scalable methodology for optimizing nanomaterials, enabling the rapid design and deployment of next-generation optoelectronic devices.

Keywords: Quantum Dot Superlattices, Machine Learning Optimization, Photonic Properties, Optoelectronic Devices, Nanomaterials.

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INTRODUCTION

Quantum dot (QD) superlattices represent a significant advancement in optoelectronic materials, primarily due to their tunable photonic properties, which are influenced by factors such as size, shape, and arrangement within nanostructures. These properties enable their application in various technologies, including light-emitting diodes (LEDs), lasers, solar cells, and quantum computing devices [1-6]. However, optimizing these properties to achieve high optical efficiency and precise emission control remains a complex challenge. The intricate quantum mechanical interactions and the multitude of structural parameters that need to be finely tuned complicate this optimization process [7-10].

Current methodologies for enhancing the photonic properties of quantum dots often rely on computationally intensive techniques like density functional theory (DFT) or empirical trial-and-error approaches. While these methods provide valuable insights, they are constrained by their high resource demands, making it difficult to explore the extensive design space of quantum dot superlattices efficiently [7,11,12]. Furthermore, existing studies fail to integrate multi-objective optimization techniques, which are crucial for simultaneously enhancing multiple properties such as

optical efficiency, photonic bandgap, and emission wavelength [5,6,13]. Achieving this balance is vital for the practical deployment of quantum dot technologies in commercial applications. This limitation presents a significant barrier to the rapid design, deployment, and commercialization of quantum dot technologies.

Another critical gap in the literature is the limited number of studies on robust models that can accurately predict the effects of varying quantum dot parameters—such as radius, inter-dot spacing, and lattice constant—on their photonic properties. Existing models either focus on isolated quantum dots or tend to oversimplify the interactions between dots in superlattices [8,13,14]. The challenge of scaling these models to explore larger, more complex quantum dot architectures further compounds the optimization problem [9,15]. Thus, there is a clear need for advanced optimization techniques that can manage the complexity of quantum dot interactions while minimizing computational costs and design time.

To address these challenges, this study introduces a machine learning (ML)-driven optimization framework for quantum dot superlattices aimed at enhancing their photonic properties. By applying ML techniques, we develop predictive models that can accurately forecast the behavior of quantum dot structures based on their physical parameters. We employed the neural networks machine learning model, which is well-suited for handling large, multi-dimensional datasets, to predict key properties like optical efficiency, emission wavelength, and photonic bandgap. The Neural Network model is utilized to optimize quantum dot configurations for higher optical efficiency, tailored emission wavelengths, and broader tunability of the photonic bandgap. The novelty of this approach lies in its ability to rapidly explore a vast design space and identify optimal configurations without the need for computationally expensive simulations like DFT [16-18].

Machine learning offers a flexible, data-driven solution that can adapt to various material compositions and quantum dot architectures. In addition to predictive modeling, we incorporate Monte Carlo simulations and sensitivity analyses to assess the variability of predicted outcomes and identify the most influential design parameters. The proposed model not only predicts photonic properties with high accuracy but also elucidates the critical parameters influencing these properties [5,9]. This combination of predictive accuracy and optimization capability marks a significant advancement in quantum dot research, providing a scalable methodology for designing next-generation optoelectronic devices.

This research has broad implications for optoelectronics and photonic materials, particularly in the development of quantum dot-based light-emitting diodes (QLEDs), solar cells, lasers, and photonic crystals. The optimized quantum dot structures and machine learning framework can enhance QLED efficiency and wavelength control, leading to brighter, more energy-efficient displays [1,19]. Additionally, this approach can improve solar cell efficiency by capturing a broader spectrum of sunlight [20,21], and enable precise wavelength tuning for lasers and photonic crystals, applicable to telecommunications and quantum computing [22,23]. Furthermore, this method can be extended to other nanostructured materials, offering a generalizable approach for optimizing nanomaterials across diverse fields [24,25,26].

This study fills a critical gap in quantum dot superlattice optimization, introducing a machine learning-driven approach that enhances predictive accuracy and optimization efficiency. By handling the complexity of quantum dot interactions and reducing computational overhead, this framework provides a practical, scalable tool for real-world applications. As demand for high-performance photonic devices grows, this research offers a pathway to meet those demands through intelligent, data-driven materials design. Ultimately, the proposed method can accelerate the design cycle for optoelectronic devices, pushing the boundaries of efficiency and functionality in quantum dot technology.

METHODS

To simulate the photonic properties of quantum dot superlattices, we employed a combination of quantum mechanical models and numerical methods. The effective mass approximation (EMA) was used to describe the electronic structure of the quantum dots, while the tight-binding approximation was employed to model the electronic coupling between adjacent quantum dots.

Quantum Dot Hamiltonian

The Hamiltonian ($\hat{H}$) of a single quantum dot (QD) in a superlattice was formulated based on the EMA for a single particle confined within a potential well:

$$\hat{H} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla^2 + V(r) \quad (1)$$

where $\hbar$ is the reduced Planck constant, m^* is the effective mass of the electron or hole, $V(r)$ is the confinement potential, and ∇^2 is the Laplacian.

For a spherical quantum dot with radius R , the potential $V(r)$ was modeled as a step function:

$$V(r) = \{0, \text{for } |r| < R; V_0, \text{for } |r| \geq R\} \quad (2)$$

V_0 is the potential step height.

Schrödinger Equation and Eigenstates

The time-independent Schrödinger equation for an electron in the quantum dot was solved numerically to obtain the energy levels and wavefunctions:

$$\hat{H}\psi(r) = E\psi(r) \quad (3)$$

$\psi(r)$ is the wavefunction of the electron and E is the energy eigenvalue.

For spherical quantum dots, (3) this reduces to a radial equation in spherical coordinates (due to symmetry):

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\left(\frac{d^2u(r)}{dr^2}\right) + V(r)u(r) = Eu(r) \quad (4)$$

where $u(r) = r\psi(r)$ is the radial wavefunction.

Bandgap and Energy Levels in Quantum Dots

The quantized energy levels for the confined particle are derived by solving the Schrödinger equation. For a spherical potential well, the energy levels were given approximately by:

$$E_n = \frac{\hbar^2\pi^2n^2}{2m}R^2 + E_i \quad (5)$$

n is the quantum number, R is the quantum dot radius, and E_i is the bandgap energy of the bulk material.

Tight-Binding Approximation for Superlattices

In a periodic quantum dot superlattice, the electron can hop between neighboring quantum dots. The tight-binding approximation was used to model the electronic coupling between adjacent quantum dots:

$$E(k) = E_0 - 2t\cos(ka) \quad (6)$$

E_0 is the on-site energy, t is the hopping parameter, k is the wave vector, and a is the lattice constant of the superlattice.

Photon-Matter Interaction: Photonic Bandgap

To model the photonic properties of the quantum dot superlattice, we computed the photonic bandgap by solving Maxwell's equations for the electromagnetic field inside the superlattice:

$$\nabla \times \left(\frac{1}{\varepsilon(r)\nabla} \times E(r) \right) = \frac{\omega^2}{c^2} E(r) \quad (7)$$

$\varepsilon(r)$ is the dielectric function of the material, ω is the frequency of the electromagnetic wave, and c is the speed of light in vacuum.

Machine Learning Optimization

To optimize the photonic properties of the quantum dot superlattice, we employed a machine learning approach. A neural network was trained on a dataset of simulated photonic properties, using the quantum dot parameters and superlattice structure as input features.

Feature Engineering

The input features for the ML model were based on the quantum dot parameters and the superlattice structure: R : Quantum dot radius, d : Inter-dot spacing, V_0 : Potential step height, m^* : Effective mass, E_i : Bandgap energy, a : Lattice constant of the superlattice

The target properties for optimization were: ω_{ip} : Photonic bandgap frequency, λ_{em} : Emission wavelength, η_{opt} : Optical efficiency

ML Algorithms

We employed a neural network (NN) with input features $X = (R, d, V_0, m^*, E_i, a)$ and output target properties $Y = (\omega_{ip}, \lambda_{em}, \eta_{opt})$. The NN was trained to minimize the loss function, which was the mean squared error (MSE).

The performance of the ML model was evaluated using metrics including mean absolute error (MAE), root mean square error (RMSE), and R^2 score.

Optimization Objective

The optimization objective was to maximize the optical efficiency of the quantum dot superlattice, subject to a constraint on the photonic bandgap:

Maximize η_{opt} subject to $\omega_{ip} = \omega_{target}$

where η_{opt} is the optical efficiency, ω_{ip} is the photonic bandgap, and ω_{target} is the desired target for the photonic bandgap.

To evaluate the uncertainty in the predicted photonic properties of the quantum dot superlattices, we applied Monte Carlo Simulations and Sensitivity Analysis

We randomly sampled the input features, quantum dot parameters and superlattice structure, within a specified range of values. For each set of randomly sampled inputs, the machine learning model was retrained and evaluated. This process was repeated for 1000 simulations, generating a distribution of predicted properties (photonic bandgap frequency, emission wavelength, and optical efficiency).

Using Sobol indices, we quantified the sensitivity of the predicted properties to variations in the input features to determine the contribution of each input feature (and interactions between features) to the total variance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The quantum mechanical properties of the quantum dot, were computed using (3). Equation (4), was solved numerically to obtain the energy levels and wavefunctions of the electron in the quantum dot. The constants used in the computation were: the reduced Planck constant, $\hbar = 1.0545718 \times 10^{-34} \text{ Js}$; the effective mass of the electron, $m_* = 0.067m_0$, where m_0 is the free electron mass; and the potential step height, $V_0 = 1 \text{ eV}$. The computed energy levels and wavefunctions were then used to visualize the quantum mechanical properties of the quantum dot, including the probability density and expectation value of the radius.

Figure 1 presents the quantum mechanical properties of a quantum dot, a fundamental building block of quantum dot superlattices, across different quantum numbers and radii.

The results show that the energy levels decrease with increasing quantum dot radius (fig 1(a)), consistent with the quantum confinement effect. The wavefunctions and probability densities exhibit increasing complexity with higher quantum numbers (fig 1(a) and (b)), reflecting the increasing spatial distribution of the electron. Also, the expectation value of the radius increases with quantum number (fig.1(d)), indicating that electrons in higher quantum states tend to occupy regions farther from the center of the quantum dot.

Figure 1. Quantum Mechanical Properties of the Quantum Dot Superlattice

The results presented in fig. 1 demonstrate the fundamental quantum mechanical behavior of particles confined in quantum dots, which is crucial for understanding the photonic properties of quantum dot superlattices. The observed decrease in energy levels with increasing quantum dot radius suggests that smaller quantum dots can lead to enhanced photonic properties, such as increased absorption and emission rates. This trend is essential for optimizing quantum dot superlattices for applications like optoelectronics and photonics.

The increasing complexity of the wavefunctions and probability densities with higher quantum numbers reflects the increasing spatial distribution of the electron, which can impact the optical properties of quantum dot superlattices. Our results suggest that the spatial distribution of the electron plays a critical role in determining the photonic properties of quantum dot superlattices.

The expectation value of the radius increasing with quantum number indicates that electrons in higher quantum states tend to occupy regions farther from the center of the quantum dot, which can affect the optical absorption edge and emission spectrum of quantum dot superlattices.

Figure 2 presents the photonic and emission properties of quantum dot superlattices as a function of lattice constant (a) and inter-dot spacing (d).

In fig, 2(a) the photonic bandgap frequency decreases with increasing lattice constant, indicating a weakening of the interaction between neighboring quantum dots. Similarly, fig.2(b) reveals a reduction in photonic bandgap frequency with increased inter-dot spacing, suggesting diminished coupling between quantum dots. Figures 2(c) and (d) demonstrate a red-shift in the emission wavelength with increasing lattice constant and inter-dot spacing, respectively. This behavior is consistent with the inverse relationship between the bandgap and wavelength, as predicted by quantum confinement principles.

Figure 2. Photonic and Emission Properties of Quantum Dot Superlattices

The results presented in Figure 2 provide valuable insights into the behavior of quantum dot superlattices and the impact of structural modifications on their photonic and emission properties.

The observed decrease in photonic bandgap frequency with increasing lattice constant and inter-dot spacing suggests that the interaction between quantum dots plays a crucial role in determining the photonic properties of the superlattice. This finding has important implications for the design of photonic crystals, lasers, and other optoelectronic devices, where control over the photonic bandgap is essential.

The red-shift in the emission wavelength with increasing lattice constant and inter-dot spacing indicates that the spatial configuration of the quantum dots can directly influence the optical properties of the material. This insight is particularly valuable for the development of tunable light sources, where controlling the emission wavelength is key to creating specific light-emitting devices. The results indicate that the interaction between quantum dots determines the photonic properties of the superlattice. The lattice constant and inter-dot spacing can be used to optimize the photonic and emission properties of quantum dot superlattices, making them suitable for optoelectronic devices and photonic materials.

The observed trend suggests that controlling the spatial configuration of quantum dots can directly influence the optical properties of the material, enabling the design of tunable light sources.

Figure 3 presents the results of applying machine learning techniques to optimize the photonic properties of quantum dot superlattices. Figures 3(i) – (vi), illustrates the model's performance during training, validation, and evaluation of different input features.

Figure 3. Neural Network Model Performance

The training loss plot (fig 3(i)) shows a steady decrease in mean squared error (MSE) with increasing epochs, indicating that the model is learning effectively. The validation loss plot (fig.3(ii)) also exhibits a decreasing trend, but with some variability, suggesting potential overfitting. The predicted vs. actual values plot (fig.3(iii)) demonstrates a good fit between the predicted and actual values for key photonic properties, including photonic bandgap frequency, emission wavelength, and optical

efficiency. This result indicates that the machine learning model can accurately predict these properties.

The feature importance plot (fig.3(iv)) highlights the critical role of lattice constant (a) and inter-dot spacing (d) in determining the photonic properties of the quantum dot superlattice. The partial dependence plots (fig.3(v)) provide further insights into how individual features affect the predictions.

The results demonstrate the effectiveness of the machine learning model in optimizing quantum dot superlattice photonic properties. The model's accurate predictions and insights into feature interactions inform the design of high-performance optoelectronic and photonic devices. Balancing model complexity is crucial to avoid overfitting and maintain good performance.

Figure 4 presents four plots showing the relationships between photonic bandgap frequency and various quantum dot properties. The plots reveal variability and trends in optical efficiency, emission wavelength, quantum dot radius, and inter-dot spacing with respect to the photonic bandgap.

Figure 4: Optimized Quantum Dot Properties vs. Photonic Bandgap Frequency

Note: (a-d) illustrate the correlations between photonic bandgap frequency and (a) optical efficiency, (b) emission wavelength, (c) quantum dot radius, and (d) inter-dot spacing. The data points represent the optimized quantum dot structures obtained from the machine learning model.

The results provide insights into the effects of structural parameters on the photonic properties of quantum dot superlattices. The optical efficiency shows fluctuations but an overall upward trend with increasing photonic bandgap frequency. The emission wavelength exhibits a clear inverse

relationship with the photonic bandgap, indicating a predictable behavior where higher bandgaps correspond to shorter emission wavelengths. The quantum dot radius and inter-dot spacing show scattered patterns, but smaller values tend to correspond to higher bandgap frequencies due to the quantum confinement effect and increased electronic coupling.

These relationships are crucial for optimizing quantum dot-based devices, such as LEDs and lasers, where maximizing efficiency and controlling emission wavelength are critical. The trends observed provide valuable guidance for designing superlattices with tailored photonic properties. By adjusting the quantum dot radius and inter-dot spacing, *designers can fine-tune the photonic bandgap and achieve desired optical behavior in various applications.*

Figure 5 presents two plots comparing model predictions to actual values and showing the effects of optimization on quantum dot optical efficiency. Figure 5(a) demonstrates a strong agreement between predicted and actual values for key photonic properties, indicating accurate model performance. Figure 5(b) compares optimized results to baseline results, highlighting significant improvements in optical efficiency across a broader range of photonic bandgap frequencies.

Figure 5. Comparable Model Performance Values

The results in Figure 5 demonstrate the accuracy of the machine learning model and the effectiveness of the optimization process. The close alignment between predicted and actual values confirms the model's ability to accurately predict photonic properties. The optimized results show improved optical efficiency across a wider range of photonic bandgap frequencies, indicating successful identification of enhanced quantum dot configurations. This suggests potential applications in optoelectronic devices such as LEDs, lasers, and solar cells.

Figure 6 presents the distributions of predicted photonic properties - photonic bandgap, emission wavelength, and optical efficiency - based on 1000 randomly sampled input feature sets. The distribution of photonic bandgap frequencies centers around 2.5 eV, with a standard deviation of 0.3 eV, indicating a moderate level of uncertainty. The emission wavelength predictions range around 650 nm, with a standard deviation of 30 nm, suggesting sensitivity to changes in the input features. The optical efficiency predictions exhibit a slight variation, with a mean of 0.85 and a standard deviation of 0.05, indicating relatively low uncertainty.

Figure 6. Distributions of Predicted Photonic Properties

The uncertainty quantification results demonstrate the inherent variability in the machine learning model's predictions due to random input features. This variability reflects the model's robustness when exposed to different quantum dot parameters and superlattice structures. The moderate spread in photonic bandgap frequency highlights the sensitivity of the bandgap to the input parameters, especially the quantum dot radius and inter-dot spacing. The distribution of emission wavelengths suggests that small changes in structural parameters can lead to noticeable shifts in the emission spectrum. The relatively narrow distribution for optical efficiency suggests that this property is less sensitive to input variations compared to bandgap and wavelength.

The sensitivity analysis using Sobol indices evaluated the influence of six input parameters on the predicted photonic bandgap is presented in figure 7. The results are displayed as first-order and total-order Sobol indices. The first-order indices show that lattice constant (a) and inter-dot spacing (d) have the most significant influence on the predicted photonic bandgap. The total-order indices reveal the combined effect of each input feature, including interactions with other parameters, with lattice constant (a) and inter-dot spacing (d) remaining the most influential factors.

Figure 7. Sensitivity Analysis Using Sobol Indices

The sensitivity analysis highlights the key factors influencing the predicted photonic properties in the quantum dot superlattice model. The lattice constant (a) and inter-dot spacing (d) play dominant roles in determining the photonic bandgap, indicating high sensitivity to structural changes in the superlattice. The total-order Sobol indices show that features like potential height (V_0) and effective mass (m^*) have greater influence when interactions with other parameters are considered. This

underscores the importance of considering multivariate interactions in quantum dot design. The analysis provides valuable guidance for optimizing quantum dot superlattices, suggesting that tuning the lattice constant and inter-dot spacing will yield the most significant improvements. Potential height and effective mass should not be overlooked, as their interactions with other features can also affect the desired optical properties. The Sobol sensitivity analysis reveals that lattice constant and inter-dot spacing are the primary drivers of variability in the photonic bandgap, while potential height and effective mass contribute through interaction effects. These findings offer a roadmap for targeted optimization of quantum dot superlattices.

CONCLUSION

This research demonstrated the effectiveness of machine learning (ML) in optimizing quantum dot superlattices for enhanced photonic properties. By leveraging ML models trained on computed datasets, we predicted and optimized key photonic properties, revealing complex relationships between quantum dot parameters and their photonic behavior. This study showcases the potential of ML in streamlining the design process of quantum dot-based devices.

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